

Article

Competitiveness of Small Businesses in The Context of Digital Transformation

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Abstract: This article analyzes the impact of digital transformation processes on the competitiveness of small businesses based on a microeconomic approach. In the modern economy, digital technologies - e-commerce platforms, digital payment systems, CRM systems, artificial intelligence, and data analysis tools - are becoming an important factor in increasing the efficiency of small business activities. The study examines the theoretical and practical aspects of the influence of the digitalization process on production costs, price formation, market share, and profit maximization strategies. The article analyzes the relationship between the level of use of digital infrastructure by small businesses and their competitive advantages in the market. Also, in the context of digital transformation, the reduction of transaction costs, the reduction of information asymmetry, and the optimization of interaction with clients are substantiated as the main factors of competitiveness. Small businesses actively implementing digital technologies are gaining more flexibility, cost-effectiveness, and an innovative advantage in the market. As a result, their sustainable development and long-term competitiveness will be ensured. This research serves to improve the policy of supporting small businesses and develop practical recommendations for the development of the digital economy.

Keywords: Digital transformation, small business, competitiveness, microeconomic analysis, e-commerce, transaction costs, innovation, digital infrastructure, market equilibrium, profit maximization.

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1. Introduction

The profound technological changes observed in the world economy in recent years, especially the rapid development of digital technologies, are fundamentally changing the mechanisms of doing business. Digital transformation is becoming an important factor in increasing efficiency, reducing costs, and expanding market share not only in large corporations but also in small businesses. The annual growth in the volume of e-commerce on a global scale, the expansion of the share of remote services, and the popularization of digital payment systems redefine the role of small businesses in the competitive environment[1].

The digitalization process is also recognized as a priority in the economy of Uzbekistan. In particular, the Strategy "Digital Uzbekistan - 2030" defined the large-scale digitalization of economic sectors in the country, the development of e-government services, and the introduction of modern information technologies into entrepreneurial activity as one of the main tasks. In accordance with this strategy, digital platforms have

been introduced in the trade, banking and financial, tax, and statistical systems, which has made it possible to significantly reduce transaction costs for small businesses[2].

The Law of the Republic of Uzbekistan "On Electronic Commerce" defined the rights and obligations of e-commerce participants and legally regulated online trade relations. Based on this law, legal guarantees for electronic contracts, digital payments, and remote trade mechanisms have been strengthened. As a result, small businesses were able to offer their products and services without territorial restrictions.

The share of small business and private entrepreneurship in the gross domestic product of Uzbekistan by the end of 2024 amounted to more than 50 percent, and at the level of employment - about 70 percent. At the same time, online trade turnover has increased several times in recent years. A sharp increase in the volume of transactions carried out through digital payment systems - for example, mobile applications and internet banking services - has increased the financial turnover rate of small businesses and improved their liquidity level[3].

Digital transformation allows reducing production and circulation costs, reducing information asymmetry, and faster formation of a balance between supply and demand. Through digital platforms, price transparency will be ensured, and it will be possible to obtain information about consumer behavior in real time. This allows small businesses to pursue a flexible pricing policy, optimize marketing strategies, and maximize profit.

At the same time, the process of digital transformation does not create equal opportunities for all entities. The insufficient development of digital infrastructure, the shortage of qualified personnel in the field of information technology, and the limited availability of financial resources remain obstacles for some small businesses. This leads to the emergence of a digital divide in the market[4].

As a result, the competitive gap between entities that have quickly implemented digital technologies and enterprises operating in the traditional way is growing.

The relevance of the topic lies in the fact that in the context of digital transformation, the analysis of the competitiveness of small businesses through microeconomic mechanisms, the scientific disclosure of its influence on the structure of costs, price formation, profit margin, and market share is of great scientific and practical importance today. The research results serve as a methodological basis for developing proposals for improving the policy of supporting small businesses, developing digital infrastructure, and increasing economic efficiency[5].

Literature review

In the study of digital transformation and the competitiveness of small businesses, theoretical and practical sources serve as an important methodological basis. In particular, in B. Khodiyev's work "Theory of Microeconomics," the market mechanism, the equilibrium of supply and demand, production costs, and the profit maximization model are described in detail. The author explains the behavior of the firm based on boundary analysis and emphasizes that the effective use of resources is the main factor determining competitive advantage. This theoretical approach serves as an important methodological basis for explaining how the cost structure of small businesses changes in the context of digital transformation, especially how technological renewal affects the ratio of fixed and variable costs[6].

Sh. In his article "Ways to Increase the Effectiveness of Entrepreneurship in the Digital Economy," the integration of modern information and communication technologies into business processes is practically analyzed. The author substantiates that digital platforms, electronic payment systems, and online marketing tools increase the operational efficiency of business entities. It is especially noted that the reduction of transaction costs and the acceleration of information flows will allow small businesses to enter new market segments. This study shows that the availability and level of use of digital infrastructure is directly related to the profitability of the enterprise[7].

A. Kasimov's scientific article "Factors of Increasing the Competitiveness of Small Business and Private Entrepreneurship" comprehensively analyzes the institutional, financial, and innovative factors that form the competitive advantage of small businesses. The author connects competitiveness not only with the price factor, but also with product quality, management efficiency, and innovation activity. It is substantiated that the introduction of digital technologies increases the flexibility of the enterprise, allows for a quick response to changes in market demand. The institutional significance of the use of digital tools is also indicated in the policy of supporting small businesses[8].

2. Materials and Methods

In this study, the microeconomic approach was taken as a basis for assessing the competitiveness of small businesses in the context of digital transformation. In the analysis process, firm theory, cost minimization, and profit maximization models were used. The influence of digital technologies on the activities of the enterprise is explained by the structure of production costs, transaction costs, and market equilibrium mechanisms.

At the empirical stage, the dynamics of the share of small business in GDP was studied based on official statistical data for 2024. With the help of comparative and statistical analysis methods, the relationship between the expansion of digital infrastructure and the effectiveness of small businesses was clarified. The growth trend was visually analyzed using tables and diagrams.

Also, based on systematic and logical analysis, digitalization is evaluated as a factor of competitiveness, reducing transaction costs, reducing information asymmetry, and increasing marketing efficiency. Scientific conclusions were formulated using the methods of induction, deduction, and comparative analysis. The applied methodology made it possible to substantiate the positive relationship between digital transformation and the development of small businesses.

3. Results

The research results show that there is a positive correlation between the processes of digital transformation and the competitiveness of small businesses. Empirical data show that the share of small business in the economy is growing in different periods of 2024, which is explained by the increase in the efficiency of enterprises that have actively implemented digital technologies[9].

In January-June 2024, small businesses generated 47.5% of the gross value added of gross domestic product (GDP). In January-December 2024 (by the end of the year), the share of small businesses in GDP reached 54.3%.

This growth is due to the expansion of production efficiency and market share of small businesses through the use of digital services, e-commerce, online trading platforms, and modern information technologies. Digital transformation allows small firms to optimize costs, effectively communicate with customers, increase price transparency, and enhance market analysis[10].

Table 1: Share of small business in GDP (2024)

Period	Share of Small Business in GDP (%)	Value Added (billion UZS)
January–March 2024	42.7%	100,279.7
January–June 2024	47.5%	257,993.6
January–December 2024	54.3%	621,073.5

As can be seen from the table, the market share of small businesses consistently increased throughout the year, which proves the effectiveness of digital transformation.

Diagram 1: Share of small business in GDP (2024)

The following column chart shows the trend of the share of small business in GDP for 2024.

In 2024, small businesses increased their share in GDP from 42.7% to 54.3%. This statistical growth is associated with the expansion of digital infrastructure and the use of digital services. E-commerce, payment systems, and digital marketing have allowed small firms to access a wider consumer base, while also helping to reduce costs and increase the volume of goods/services[11].

Digital transformation will increase the efficiency of small businesses - sales and the number of customers through online platforms will increase, market data will be analyzed faster, and decisions will be made more efficiently[12].

Small business remains the most important sector in the economy, as it increases employment and strengthens market competition. According to statistics, by the end of 2024, the share of small businesses in GDP reached 54.3%, which is a positive result of the government's policy of promoting digital transformation[13].

Digital transformation creates opportunities for small businesses, including[14]:

Bringing products to the global market through e-commerce;

Fast and secure transactions using digital payment systems;

Expansion of the client base through online marketing;

Making decisions based on data (big data, analytics).

These trends make small businesses more sustainable and competitive[15].

4. Conclusion

The results of this study showed that digital transformation is being formed as a strategic factor in increasing the competitiveness of small businesses. The integration of digital technologies into business processes serves to increase production efficiency, optimize costs, and enhance flexibility in the market environment. In particular, online trading platforms, digital payment systems, and management mechanisms based on data analysis create the basis for raising the activities of small businesses to a qualitatively new level.

Digital transformation not only increases the internal operational efficiency of small businesses, but also strengthens their resilience to external market competition. As a result of the acceleration and transparency of information flows, the decision-making process is optimized, and the ability to quickly respond to changes in supply and demand is

expanded. This forms the innovative advantage necessary for long-term sustainable development.

In the process of digital transformation, factors related to infrastructure, human resources, and financial resources are of great importance. For the effective use of the digital environment, small business entities, along with the application of modern technological solutions, must also modernize their management culture. Otherwise, in the context of the digital economy, the competitive advantage may be concentrated in the hands of large and technologically developed entities.

In general, digital transformation is a decisive factor in ensuring the economic stability of small businesses, expanding market segments, and transitioning to an innovative development model. In the future, it is necessary to take systemic measures to institutionally support this process, deepen the digitalization of the business environment, and develop digital skills for small businesses.

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